

Geology and Petrography of Migmatite Rocks around Bagel and Its Environs, Bauchi North-Eastern Nigeria

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Accepted July 03, 2021

Published July 06, 2021

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DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5076227>

Pages: 14-26

Funding: None

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How to cite this article (APA):
Nuruddeen, A., & Ahmad Isah, H. (2021). Geology and Petrography of Migmatite Rocks around Bagel and Its Environs Bauchi, North-Eastern Nigeria. *North American Academic Research*, 4(6), 14-26. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5076227>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The study area is part of sheet 149SW Bauchi, which falls within the Northern basement Complex of Nigeria. In this study, area was mapped on a scale of 1:25,000. Samples were collected at the flanks of the outcrops, railway cuts, road cuts as well as quarry sites within the area. At each sampling point, two or more samples were collected based on morphological variations. The first and the second order morphological classifications of migmatites as being metatexite or Diatexite such as banded orthogneiss, stromatic schleiren or nebulite were used as the guiding principle. This technique was repeated for the rest of the sampling points in the area. A total of 35 samples were collected, 11 representative samples were studied macroscopically and Petrographically. Together with the field mapping and morphological features, it was observed that the area has four different four(4) different lithologic units, vis: Metatexite(Banded Orthogneiss), Mesocratic, leucocratic and melanocratic diatexites in a sequence of prograde metamorphism where the volume of melt generated during the anatexis; H₂O-fluxed melting(metatexite) and Muscovite Dehydration(Diatexite) mechanism determines degree of anatexis and morphological unit of Migmatite, and CO₂(graphite) aids in enhancing the temperature needed for the exceptional coarse grains textures of Quartzofelspathic portions of the Migmatite, yet through rapid cooling. Garnet and Sillimanite dissemination within the petrographic slides, signifies the terrain as granulite Facies.

Keywords: PELITE SCHIST, BANDED ORTHOGNEISS, DIATEXITE, MESOCRATIC, MELANOCRATIC, LEUCOCRATIC, SCHLEIREN, GRANULITE FACIES, METASEDIMENT, PROGRADE METAMORPHISM, GRAPHITE,

1.0 Introduction

The rocks of the study area were earlier study by Falconer(1911), Bain(1926), Oyawoye(1959,1961,1965), Dada et al.(2012), Haruna(2016) and Yahuza(2020). This present work is aimed to investigate the morphological forms of rocks in light of prograde metamorphism. The study area is located on sheet 149SW, Bauchi which lies between latitudes 10°02'00" N and 10°06'00" N, North of the Equator and longitudes longitude 9°35'00" E and 9°40'00" E east of the Green meridian. It covers a total landmass of about 63.48 square kilometers and is accessible through the main road, Bauchi-Dass and other numerous footpaths. The

topography is characterized by highland and flat topography with outcrops of low, moderately and high level elevation that ranges from 500m to about 890m. River Bagel is the only major river in the study area and has its sources in the high land around the Jos Plateau. It's however fed by many tributaries and in turn runs into river [Gongola, Yahuza\(2020\)](#).

1.1 Literature Review: [Oyawoye \(1959\)](#), concluded that most of Nigeria was probably covered by sedimentary rocks which were metamorphosed to schists, quartzites, amphibolites and calcisilicates in the normal cycle of regional metamorphism during the Precambrian times. These are still found over most of the country where not obscured by Cretaceous sedimentary rock or completely granitized, as in the Bauchi District. In the Bauchi District, the metasedimentary rocks appear to have been converted to granulites with irregular masses of calcisilicate rocks. From these granulites, the evolution of the present Bauchi rocks began with the interstitial development of microcline and a corresponding decrease in the proportion of biotite. Most of the early components for the microcline are taken from the biotite and the downward migration of the basic material must have started very early. This process, if it could be called granitization, was controlled by the planes of schistosity and differential rates of development lead to the development of the lit-par-lit gneiss. As the process advanced, the intervening bands of granulite also succumbed to granitization and only short parallel streaks of biotite and few schlieren were left to indicate their former presence. Thus the biotite gneiss was evolved, [Oyawoye\(1959\)](#). From here on, the course of granitization is reflected in the field mainly by textural changes. There is a marked and progressive, though not entirely gradual, disappearance of the original fine grained granular texture and the emergence of medium to coarse porphyroblastic aggregates [Oyawoye\(1959\)](#). [King and De Swardt\(1949\)](#) remarked on a similar trend of development in the Osi area of Nigeria. Although the microcline porphyroblasts tend to grow with their longer axes in the plane of foliation of the rock, the general effect of their development is to obliterate the gneissose appearance and alter the rock progressively towards one of granitic aspect [Oyawoye\(1959\)](#). These transformations are believed to fall within the normal cycle of regional metamorphism and to have been under the temperature and pressure conditions equivalent to the amphibolite-granulite facies [Oyawoye\(1959\)](#). The intensity appears to be normally a function of depth though subject to many variables whose influences are not well known, among them: extraneous heat from consolidating abyssal magma, fluid emanation affecting change of temperature and or fluid pressure, stress and the bulk composition of the metamorphism, [Kings\(1949\)](#). Acting separately or in concert, these would tend to make the intensity of granitization completely varied, at a given plane in a plutonic series. Thus in Bauchi one is still able to observe the various stages in the developments from lit-par-lit gneiss to the Biotite-Hornblend Granite despite the deep erosion, [Oyawoye\(1959\)](#). This principal stages in the development form aureoles around the core of Quartz-Diorite from where, it would appear to emanate heat and solution. The mineralogical redistribution of rocks components in an effort to reach a stage of equilibrium under plutonic conditions, [Oyawoye\(1959\)](#). And [Soesoo and Bond, Soesoo\(2014\)](#) proposed that during melt segregation and transport the system is controlled by self-organized criticality that governs the topology of

magmatic bodies from migmatitic leucosomes to pluton and Batholiths.

2.0 Materials and methods

The method of mapping along profiles from one outcrop to another taking note of road and railway cuts as well as quarry sites that revealed sub-surface lithology was used in a systematic manner in the field in order to understand the geology of the area, [Aga\(2018\)](#). Structural measurements were taken using compass clinometer, while samples of fresh rocks units were taken at each location with coordinates, labeled using hammer, GPS and pens. The first and Second order morphological classifications of [Sawyer\(2008\)](#) and [Hasalova et al.,\(2008\)](#) were used as the guiding principle. This technique was repeated for the rest of the sampling points in the study area covering about ten(10) different locations. A total of 35 samples were collected. The 35 samples collected were sorted and grouped into 11 on the basis of morphology. From each group, each representative sample were studied macroscopically and microscopically(petrographic) in the laboratory. Petrographic analysis involves the description of a sample in thin section using the optical microscope in the lab. This is more detailed than the macroscopic study, which involves looking at the rock sample with naked eye or through a hand lens to observe the color, texture, mineralogy and composition¹⁵. The thin section were prepared at ATBU petrographic lab and a polished thin sections were analysed at Thin-section Laboratory of Of ATAP Bauchi, Nigeria from the 11 selected fresh samples for petrographic studies.

The thin section of each sample was viewed in two modes, the first with the analyser out to produce or give the Plane-Polarised Light(PPL). In this mode, properties such as color, pleochroism, form, cleavage, relief and alteration could be observed. After this, the same slide viewed with analyser-in, the Cross-Polarized Light(XPL). In this mode, mineral properties such as interference colors, extinction angle, twinning and birefringence could be observed, [Abdulraouf\(2014\)](#). Finally, the result of field relationship, macroscopic study, microscopic study were married together to come-up with clear understanding of morphological units of different migmatites of the study area, related to the relevant authors.

2.1 Results

This sub-section presents the results of the analyzed samples which comprises the field relationship, morphological units and petrographic result. Eleven (11) Representative samples from the field, Fig8, were coded as; Banded Orthogneiss Metatexite(**A1,A2**), **figure 1 and 2**. Mesocratic Diatexite(**C1,C2,C3**), **figure 3**. Melanocratic Diatexite(**B1,B2,B3**), **figure 4** and Leucocratic diatexite(**D1,D2,D3**), **figure5**.

Figure 1: Field view occurrence of Metatexite (Banded Orthogneiss); **a.** Paleosome (Pelitic schist) underlain the Diatexite **b:** Leucosome and paleosome segregated (felsic bands), trending E-W foliation plane dipping between 30° - 40° . **c:** Garnet bearing banded orthogneiss with dissemination of garnet index minerals with some ptygmatic fold.

Figure 2a. Hand specimen description of Garnet bearing Banded orthogneiss showing Mafic lineation **b1.** Photomicrograph of Garnet bearing Banded orthogneiss (**b1**) Under Plane polarized light PPL, and (**b2**) Cross polarized light CPL. Minerals of the Rock are; Qtz = quartz, Plg = plagioclase, Grt = garnet, Bt = biotite, Sil = Sillimanite, Cor = cordierite.

Figure 3: Photograph of Diatexite Migmatite . A Melanocratic diatexite transitional zone. Showing leucosome. B= Hand description. C:Photomicrograph of Melanocratic diatexite, C1: under Plane polarized light(PPL) and C2: Under cross polarized light(CPL). Minerals of the Rock are; Qtz = quartz, Plg = plagioclase, Bt = biotite, Sil= Sillimanite, Cor= cordirite.

Figure.4: Mesocratic Diatexite Migmatite; a: Field view Occurrence of Mesocratic diatexite, indicating mafic schlieren alternate with quartzofelapatic veins b: Hand specimen description showing magmatic foliation. c: Photomicrograph, C1. Under Plane polarized light(PPL) and C2. Under cross polarized light(CPL). Minerals of the Rocks are; Qtz = quartz, Plg = plagioclase, Bt = biotite, Sil= Sillimanite, Cor= cordirite.

Figure.5: Leucocratic Diatexite; a: Field view of transition from Leucocratic diatexite and granulitic granite. b: Hand specimen description of leucocratic diatexite showing homogeneous granitic texture. **C1:** Photomicrograph of Leucocratic diatexite under PPL and **C2.** Under cross polarized light(CPL). Minerals of the Rock are; Qtz = quartz, Plg = plagioclase, Mic=microcline.

2.1.1 Geology of the area: (Geological map, figure6), the oldest rock of the study area is metasediment; Pelitic schist(Paleosome-Oldest) forms as patches, sporadically within the Metatexite (Banded orthogneiss,(figure1a,b & c). Though other metasediment like quartzite in fadaman mada, [Yahuza\(2020\)](#) and others, granulite, amphibolite and calcisilicate rocks are the paleosomes of other plutonic rocks of Bauchi and transforms to various grade of metamorphic rocks during the regional metamorphism/ Pan-african Orogeny. This followed by prograde sequence of Banded Orthogneiss to Mesocratic, melanocratic and leucocratic(youngest unit)diatexite migmatite. The rocks are classified in table-1 modified from information of [Oyawoye\(1959\)](#).

Table-1: Rock Classification in order of Proble Age

S/no	Rock Type	Description
5	Leucocratic diatexite migmatite	Diatexit with well define granite texture, high developed K-Felspar with porphyroblastic texture---- Youngest
4	Melanocratic Diatexite	Diatexite with Raft and Schollen of paleosome
3	Mesocratic Diatexite	Diatexite withs more Biotite-rich mafic schleiren, pinch and swell structures
2	Banded Orthogneiss Metatexite	Metatexite with Distinctive regular banding; neosome and paleosome
1	Metasediment: Paleosome	Pelitic schist ---- Oldest

Figure 6: Geological map of the study area showing different morphological forms of migmatite.

2.1.2 Field Relationship, Morphology, Macroscopic and Microscopic Descriptions:

2.1.2.1 Metatexite: Banded Orthogneiss(A1 and A2): Banded orthogneiss(Figure 1&2) is well exposed more along River Bagel. With patches of paleosome metatexite coexist and overlain by diatexite (Figure1a). They are not as extensive as the other rocks found within the study area, in most of the areas in field view and hand specimen, it occurs as garnet bearing banded orthogneiss (Figure1b,c & 2a), it is very dark brown with porphyroblastic index mineral(garnet) disseminated all over, which makes it very coarse grain in texture(Figure1b). Morphologically, the metatexite is called banded orthogneiss because of distinctive regular banding of neosome and paleosome, [Hasalova et al.,\(2008\)](#), medium grains and very dark gray in color, the banding is regular in form and consists of two components – a paleosome and a neosome alternates one another (Figure1b & 2a). The foliation plane is defined not only by the parallelism of the biotite

crystals, but by alternative bands of leucosome and paleosome generally trending E-W, dipping with their entire planes at about 30° to 40° (Plate1b).

Photomicrograph, (plate2b1 & b2); In Plane polarized light(PPL) and cross polarized light(XPL), Garnet minerals are porphyroblastic grains and anhedral, irregular fractures, high relief, with some minutes inclusion of quartz and biotite minerals, and bounded by some elongated moderate relief biotites and form part of the paleosome, while the Quartz, plagioclase and some sillimanite show grey to colorless, quartz shows undulose extinction, no relief, light brown pleochroic, concoidal fractures, Plagioclase with two directional cleavage predominate the felsic minerals and form part of the leucosome.

2.1.2.2 Melanocratic diatexite(B1,B2,B3): Melanocratic diatexite (Figure3a,b) was mapped around Mararraba LK, Tola, and Dajin as low-medium outcrop, very thick irregular melanocratic bands alternate with of quartzofelspatic thicks bands and few thin biotite rich schlieren bands defined the foliation planes. Morphologically, sporadical distribution of raft and schollen of paleosome, with highest biotite content than other diatexite defined the diatexite Sawyer(2008) and Abdulraouf(2014):

Photomicrograph, (Figure3c1 and c2) indicated that, melanocratic diatexite, under PPL; Leucocratic part (Quartz and Plagioclase) shows no relief, colorless to grey pleochroic, contorted, rolled and flow by magmatic shear stress along a melanosome. Biotite shows elongation in preferred orientation, high relief, anhedral, one directional cleavage, sillimanite occur as fibres within the space between the biotite crystals, brown to grey pleochroic, and also elongated in preferred orientation, cordierite, high medium relief, anhedral, yellow pleochroic halo, randomly scatter within the biotite, sillimanite and plagioclase.

2.1.2.3 Mesocratic diatexite(C1,C2,C3): Mesocratic diatexite(Figure4a,b) was developed around jamda and mararraba, low outcrop, in field view generally is medium to coarse grain, relatively uniform texture, schollen and raft are gradually destroying to parallel biotite rich shleiren alternate and cross-cutting quartzofelspatic veins and mosly define the Pan-african structures, N-E and NE-SW. Morphologically, is defined as mesocratic diatexite because of its parallel Biotite-rich schleiren alternate with quartzofelspatic leucosomes, pinch and swollen at irregular patterns Abdulraouf(2014):

Photomicrograph indicated, Plane polarized light(PPL); Cordierite, Sillimanite, biotite and graphite(CO₂) are the major melanosome minerals, Grapgitte is Opaque, cordierites have high relief, yellow pleochroic halo, very dark, anhedral, randomly scattered and intergrowth within the biotite and plagioclase. In Cross Polarized light (XPL); Myrmekite developed at the boundary between the plagioclase and quartz intergrowth with biotite which shows the fluid flow magmatic transformation.

2.1.2.4 Leucocratic diatexite(D1,D2,D3): Leucocratic Diatexite(Figure5) was developed around the jamda and mararraba, low outcrop, in field view, generally is medium to coarse grain, relatively uniform texture, developments of granulitic granite/quartzofelspatic at the flanks and coexist with the leucocratic diatexite(figure5a) and consuming the diatexite and forms a transsional boundary, the biotite schleiren streaks

from mesocratic are homogenized (figure 5b), Granulitic granite at the flanks form a porphyroblastic texture, biotite rich schlieren if any, crenulate around boundary between feldspatic porphyroblast and diatexite (figure 5a). Morphologically, is classified as Leucocratic diatexite because of its uniform texture (well define igneous texture), more K-felspar development, and small or no dykes or sill cross-cutting (Abdulraouf(2014)).

Petrographically, (figure 5b,c), microcline shows cross-hatch twinning, polysynthetic twin by albite plagioclase, undulatory extinction by quartz, intergrowth between plagioclase and microcline depict the pathetic microstructure.

2.1.3 Discussion of Result:

The four (4) major principal rocks are morphologically distinguished in the study area: i. Banded orthogneiss (metatexite) . iii. Mesocratic diatexite, iii. Melanocratic diatexite, iv. Leucocratic diatexite

This section presents the discussion of the morphology, petrographic results and compare with other authors.

2.1.4 Morphological Features: In most cases, the contact between the rocks is transitional. Interestingly, the metasediment (Pelitic schist)/Metatexite is the paleosome, dark brown, well foliated trending east-west overlain by diatexite (figure 1a). It is only found in one location in River bagel within the study area (figure 6). This is one of the metasediments that constitute the Bauchi rocks as reported by Oyawoye(1959) and Bain(1926). At the incipient stage of anatectic process, metasediments were progressively start to metamorphose partially to metatexite (figure 1a) by water (H₂O)-fluxed melting (Malord et al.,(2020)), (figure 7). The degree of partial melting was limited by rapid exhaustion of the available water, but generated a melt fraction in excess which migrate short distance (Malord et al.,(2020)) along E-W foliation planes (figure 1b,c) of schist (paleosome), the melt fractions were manifested as Ptygmatic fold, felsic band, lensoid, and veins-like leucosome (figure 1b,c and 2a) and pre-migmatic layering and foliation planes of schist survived the partial melting, therefore the schist transformed to Banded Orthogneiss metatexite migmatite, which is more of rock rheology (figure 1a,b and 2a) (Malord et al.,(2020)). Banded Orthogneiss metatexite characterised with a regular banding of Paleosome and quartzo-felspatic leucosome, porphyroblastic garnet as an indices of granulite facies, the quartzofelspatic and paleosome are entirely dipping entirely between 30⁰-40⁰ east-west as modified from report of Oyawoye(1959) and Bain(1926), mentioned as granulites or Hornfel granulite. Disseminated porphyroblastic garnet is an indices of high grade granulite metamorphic terrane (figure 1b, c).

With more progressive increase in temperature, more anatectic process, the Banded orthogneiss began to underwent further reaction, a Muscovite dehydration melting generated a much larger and more pervasive melt fraction (Malord et al.,(2020)), (figure 7). This larger melt fraction flows and obliterated the Pre-migmatic schistose structures of Banded Orthogneiss and ultimately forms a, Mesocratic, Leucocratic and Melanocratic diatexites (figure 4a,5a, and 3a), as modified from Oyawoye(1959) and Bain(1926) as, mixed gneiss and pegmatite and Lit-par-lit gneiss, Biotite gneiss and Biotite granite, and Agmatitic gneiss respectively. When

melt-residuum separation attained, Mesocratic transforms to Melanocratic, when less than 40% of melt fraction extracted from partially melted mesocratic diatexite, while Leucocratic diatexite forms only if melt fraction extracted out from mesocratic is more than 40%. (figure 3a & 5a, and figure 12) Malord et al., (2020).

2.1.5 Petrographical Features: The presence of high temperature index minerals, Sillimanite, Garnet, and Cordirite in almost all the samples (Figure 2, 3, 4) signifies a granulite facies, Daniel (1990). Most of the twinning fashions in the plagioclase (Labradorite or Bytownite) in petrographic slide is Polysynthetic twinning, except some cross-hatch twin in Leucocratic diatexite (figure 5b), which shows progressive development of K-feldspar from Metatexite to Diatexite (Leucocratic diatexite). The Quartz in all the samples (figure 2, 3, 4, 5), shows Undulatory extension which indicated high level of deformational stress, and extent of metamorphism. The opaque mineral (Figure 3c, 4c and 5c) is graphite, sourced CO₂ both from mantle and at the surface from the existing carbonate rocks. During the collisional zone regional metamorphism, CO₂ heat up the system enough to form very coarse grains (Leucocratic part of figure 2b, 3b, 4b and Figure 5b) through metamorphic process (Carbonic dehydration) Clemens (1990). The fractures connecting the opaque minerals in the plates signifies penetration of the CO₂ and their orientation in same direction means the stress was regional not Magmatic, Yahuza et al., (2020).

Figure 6. Process of Anatexis of Metasedimentary Protolith (Tuttle and Bowen, 1958)

3.0 Conclusion

The study area is part of sheet 149SW which falls within the Northern Basements Complex of Nigeria. In this study, the area was mapped on a scale of 1:25,000. Detail fieldwork was carried out, 35 fresh samples were

collected based on morphological variations as being metatexite or diatexite. Samples were sorted and grouped accordingly into 4 groups; Banded Orthogneiss Metatexite, Mesocratic, Leucocratic, and melanocratic diatexite. 11 representative samples out of 35 were selected. Petrographic slides were prepared at Thin Section Laboratory of ATBU Bauchi, and also Petrographic slides were studied at ATAP Bauchi Petrographic Laboratory were studied under both Plane and Cross Polarised Light (PPL & XPL), clear shots were taken. From the field and laboratory results, the following conclusions may be drawn: i. Banded Orthogneiss (metatexite), were progressively formed from Pelitic schist that still exist as remnants and sporadically distributed within the Banded Orthogneiss. This is evidence in their field occurrence at River Bagel, the Pre-migmatic structures survived and are trending E-W conformable with the Schistose structures and presence of high temperature minerals (Garnet, Sillimanite, Cordierite and calc plagioclase) signifies the granulite metamorphic facies. ii. Mesocratic diatexite forms during Muscovite dehydration melting, at high anatectic magmatic activities from Banded Orthogneiss, where higher melt fraction generated from paleosome which obliterates the former schistose structure, and reactivated the schistose structures E-W to Pan-African N-E, NE-SW structures. Evidence from the field occurrence shows that mesocratic at Jamda and Mararraba are well exposed at low to medium outcrops and presence of high temperature minerals (Sillimanite, Graphite, Cordierite, Biotite), and Quartz and Plagioclase formed major part of Paleosome and Neosome. iii. Melanocratic diatexite, was formed from high residuum enriched part of mesocratic diatexite when the less than 40% of melt were expelled out of the Mesocratic. Raft and schollen of paleosome preserved and field occurrences, exposed at Marraba LK, Tula and Dajin. Petrographically, Sillimanite, Cordierite, Graphites, Quartz, Plagioclase are the prominent minerals. iv. Leucocratic Diatexite transformed from more enriched melt (More than 40%) part of Mesocratic diatexite, and temperature of crystallization was aided by CO₂ (graphite), which enable the grains to grow very coarse yet through rapid cooling.

3.1 Recommendation

Based on the result obtained from the field and laboratory analyses carried out, the following recommendations are made: **i.** Geochemistry has to be carried out to understand the melting segregation mechanism, Water fluxed and Muscovite dehydration melting to properly come up with metatexite-Diatexite transformational genesis. **ii.** The structural analysis has to be also carried out in detail to ascertain the general structural trend of Paleo and Neo migmatitic structures **iii.** Furthermore, a lot of hydrothermal activities occurred at transitional boundaries and at large, during transformation of schist to diatexite. Therefore, economic potential of the study area should be carried out to come up with economic viability of the study area, as Gold mineralization has already been discovered at some metatexite areas.

3.2 Acknowledgements

The Authors appreciate the effort/contributions of the following: i. Applied geology department ATBU Bauchi for assisting in thin section preparation. ii. Abubakar Tatari Ali Polytechnic Bauchi for Tri-nocular petrographic microscope for Petrographic studies. iii. My field Assistance, Abukakar Keso and Sadiq

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